

From task completion to learning progress: Shifting mathematics teachers' conceptualisations of success as a key challenge in professional growth

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Abstract

Heterogeneous conceptualisations of success in mathematics instruction influence what is strived for in mathematics classrooms, this is widely discussed for policy perspectives, student perspectives, and classroom observer perspectives. In each case, alignment to assessment has been identified as critical condition. This plenary paper adds to this discourse a fourth perspective, the teacher perspective, by summarizing research findings from professional development research projects that identify teachers' individual categories for successful mathematics teaching as critical for instructional practices and for their pathways of professional growth. In particular, the examples show that teachers' success category of task completion often dominates their practices. When they shift to success categories concerning learning progress, their pathways of professional growth can accelerate.

Keywords: Teacher professional development, conceptualisation of success, task completion

Introduction

The MEI conference theme "Conceptualising Success in Mathematics Education" is described on the website as follows: "The discourse relating to success in mathematics education is populated with reference to student achievement and proficiency on standardised examinations" and announces "a space to investigate what – and who – constitutes success in mathematics education, and how this is achieved". This plenary paper intends to contribute through teacher professional development (PD) research, by investigating and promoting teachers' conceptualisations of success for mathematics teaching and learning. Rather than presenting one classical research report, research findings from several PD research projects in our research group are synthesized. Section 1 gives with a brief overview on different perspectives on conceptualisations of success in mathematics classrooms, deriving why research on teacher perspectives could be essential. Section 2 briefly introduces the theoretical background, and Section 3 presents findings from several research projects on the role of a prevalent success category, task completion. Section 4 widens to further projects and Section 5 discusses the investigated teacher perspective in connection to other perspectives.

1. Different perspectives on conceptualisations of success

This section starts from conceptualisations of success of mathematics instruction, which can be defined as those prescriptions that guide different stakeholders' evaluations or actions for developing mathematics instruction. Section 2–4 will then narrow it down to teachers' implicit or explicit success categories that guide their instructional practices.

1.1 *Policy perspectives and constructive alignment of state assessments*

From a policy perspective, conceptualisations of success are prescriptions from state educational authorities as to what schools and teachers should aim at.

From a *policy curriculum perspective*, the most frequent approach to conceptualising success of mathematics instruction is to prescribe the learning goals that schools should strive to achieve. Since mandatory schooling had been established as a public responsibility some centuries ago, the learning goals were successively codified in national, state or district curricula (syllabi and textbooks, later also in standards). Since the 1960s, the scope of these official curricula were increasingly extended to more ambitious learning goals, from procedural skills in arithmetic to skills in algebra and geometry and then to also include conceptual understanding (Clements et al., 2013), further mathematical domains (e.g. set theory and probabilities), and since the 1980s increasingly also mathematical practices such as modelling, problem solving, arguing and others (Cockcroft Report, 1982; Silver & Lane, 1993). So, from the policy curriculum perspective, we might summarize that policy conceptualisations of the success of mathematics instruction have become more and more ambitious.

However, many observations of conditions for curriculum reforms to be implemented revealed that extensions in syllabi, standards, and curricula do not necessarily impact mathematics classroom practices as long as the state assessments do not cover the whole range of extended learning goals. This basic idea of *constructive alignment* was prominently articulated in the influential Cockcroft Report (1982) and later summarized as “What you test is what you get” (Burkhardt et al., 1990, see also Biggs, 1996). This observation led to efforts for enhancing the coverage of assessments to include all relevant learning goals, not only for high-stakes state assessments, but also for (summative and formative) assessment for learning (Silver & Lane, 1993; Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2018), resulting in an increasing discourse on conceptual understanding and mathematical practices as relevant learning goals in mathematics instruction. But already Burkhardt et al. (1990) emphasized that what is tested in state assessments can influence what is *taught*, but not necessarily what is *learned* by all students.

So, a second *policy perspective* concerns the increasing emphasis on *equitable access for all students*, so that not only a small minority gets access to ambitious learning goals (Clements et al., 2013). While in most OECD countries, the goal of formal institutional access to schooling is widely achieved (Callahan, 2005), the dominant *conceptualisation of success with regard to equitable access* also refers to all students’ opportunities for *achieving* in mathematics, not only their presence in classrooms (OECD, 2016). Most educational systems fail to provide such equitable access, as continuously documented by unequally distributed mathematics achievements in large-scale assessments for students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, diverse language proficiencies, learning disabilities or other diverse abilities (OECD, 2016; Faragher, Hill & Clarke, 2016). Schools’ failure can often be traced back to opportunity gaps through low-quality teaching (Boaler, 2002; DIME, 2007).

The discourse about inequitable achievement has been problematized as a “gap-gazing fetish” (Gutiérrez, 2008) that is too restricted to too narrow educational goals and fuels deficit

views on students from marginalized backgrounds. While I would totally agree that the persistent hint to social or immigration-related achievement gaps risks strengthening stereotypes and has its own contribution in reproducing inequitable learning opportunities (Boaler, 2002; Wilhelm et al., 2017), this deconstruction does not yet automatically lead to other constructive approaches to empower students from marginalized backgrounds. So, we need to continue to develop approaches for enhancing *all* students' mastery of ambitious learning goals, such as conceptual understanding of mathematics.

1.2 Student perspectives and the challenge of focusing assessments

With regard to *students'* learning, studies in learning sciences have repeatedly shown that attainment of ambitious learning goals (such as conceptual understanding or mathematical practices) requires students' deep cognitive engagement, whereas shallow cognitive processes can mainly serve more superficial learning goals (like facts or procedural knowledge) (Chi et al., 2018; Hiebert & Grouws, 2007).

But this might not necessarily be reflected in subjective conceptualisations of success from *students' perspective*. For students, a successful mathematics lesson might be one in which deep cognitive engagement was not necessary. Illusions of understanding for example can subjectively substitute deep cognitive engagement, as when students love certain YouTube videos more than their teachers' explanations even if they do not retain the presented knowledge aspects (Kulgemeyer, 2020).

Already Nicholls, Cobb, and colleagues (1990) investigated how students conceptualise success in mathematics classrooms and found that some students conceptualised success as being better than their peers, other students by gained understanding. The latter group believed also more in the worth of efforts in classrooms. This early finding resonates with Dweck's (1996) often-cited distinction into mastery orientation and performance orientation: students with mastery orientation strive for developing mastery in the content to be learned, whereas students with performance orientation strive for demonstrating their competence without necessarily improving mastery. Students with mastery orientation usually appreciate deep cognitive engagement more than students with performance orientation who might, e.g., misinterpret a productive struggle as a sign of bad performance.

For both, students with performance orientation and with mastery orientation, the alignment of assessments to the articulated learning goals is crucial: when the assessments suggest that shallow knowledge is sufficient, then students with mastery orientation might not even be aware of the depth that could be reached. Leber et al. (2018) showed that even for university students who voluntarily participated in a course with explicitly articulated conceptual learning goals, constructive alignment matters: for half of the students, a mis-aligned fact-oriented test was announced. The other half of the students who expected the aligned understanding-oriented test used significantly deeper elaboration strategies than in the group expecting a fact-oriented test.

To sum up student perspectives, students' individual conceptualisations of success and external success criteria set by assessments can impact students' learning processes substantially.

1.3 *Classroom observer perspective*

In several decades of classroom research, quality dimensions for effective mathematics instruction that lead to higher learning outcomes have been identified, in particular classroom management, high cognitive demands, conceptual focus, and instructional support (Brophy, 2000; Hiebert & Grouws, 2007; Pianta & Hamre, 2009). But research findings alone do not lead to increasing classroom quality: mathematics teachers in most countries continue to enact mathematics teaching with strongly varying qualities (e.g., TALIS study, OECD, 2020). Among many other factors such as some teachers' limited access to pedagogical content knowledge (PCK, Shulman, 1986) or challenging external conditions in under-resourced classrooms, it was shown that heterogeneous *conceptualisations of successful teaching* (e.g., in the so-called visions of good teaching, Cobb & Jackson, 2021) can be an important factor explaining varying qualities of enacted teaching.

Heterogeneous conceptualisations of successful teaching have been documented in a study about observers' criteria for selecting effective teaching (Strong et al., 2011). Video-clips with teaching episodes were shown to school administrators, teacher leaders, mentors, and teacher educators to select the effective / non-effective teachers (by subjectively inferring who might induce high / low learning gains). The observers selected the effective teachers only with 31% – 47% accuracy (below probability of guessing), with individual success criteria that deviated substantially from the quality dimensions in the consolidated state of classroom quality research. Most often, observers applied surface criteria for successful teaching (e.g., small group work, use of visuals and manipulatives for hands-on activities), not the deeper structures of effective teaching (e.g., depths of minds-on activities).

These findings on *classroom observer perspectives* are remarkable because classroom observations by teacher educators and administrators can be considered as the typical assessment for teachers, and again, alignment with the regular goals seems critical but cannot be taken for granted. Indeed, alignment in the visions of good teaching between school administrators, headmasters, teacher educators, coaches, and teachers has been identified as a decisive condition for jointly developing teaching quality (Cobb & Jackson, 2021).

1.4 *Research focus: Investigating and enhancing teachers' perspectives on success as critical factors for professional growth*

The persistence of low-quality teaching, in particular in classrooms with many underprivileged students (Boaler, 2002; DIME; 2007), and the findings about the needed shared vision of successful teaching (Cobb & Jackson, 2021) raises the question about teachers' individual conceptualisations of successful teaching and the connection to their practices.

The deviations in conceptualisations that were sketched in the brief literature review from several perspectives, the policy curriculum perspective, the policy equity perspective, the student perspective, and the classroom observer perspective, suggest that also teachers' individual conceptualisations might be a) heterogeneous. In the following, we will argue that they might also be b) influential for teachers' practices, c) a hindrance for professional growth, and/or d) when shifted, then a potential motor for professional growth. Within the theoretical framework that will be outlined in the next section, the paper collects findings

from several PD research projects of our research group with regard to three research questions:

- How are teachers' practices influenced by their conceptualisations of success?
- How are teachers' pathways of professional growth influenced by conceptualisations of success?
- How can shifts in teachers' conceptualisations of success be initiated, and how do they impact the professional growth of instructional practices?

2. **Theoretical framework for describing and explaining the role of teachers' conceptualisations of success for practices and pathways of professional growth**

For describing and explaining the role of teachers' conceptualisations of success for their instructional practices, our research group draws upon the *Framework of Content-Related Teacher Expertise* (Prediger, 2019 adapted from Bromme, 1992 and Schoenfeld, 2010) that combines cognitive perspectives on teachers' knowledge and attitudes with situated perspectives on teaching practices (Depaepe et al., 2013). Five constructs are used to explain teachers' practices as recurrent answers for typical situational demands (jobs) by means of the underlying components:

- *Jobs*: typical and often complex situational demands that teachers have to master in classrooms (in each PD project, we focus on specific jobs of relevance for the PD content in view, for example fostering at-risk students' understanding).
- *Practices*: recurrent patterns of teachers' utterances and actions for managing the jobs – teachers' practices can be characterized by the underlying categories, pedagogical tools, and orientations upon which teachers implicitly or explicitly draw:
 - *Pedagogical tools*: tangible or visible tools applied to manage the jobs (e.g., facilitation moves, assessment tasks, manipulatives, or other instructional artifacts).
 - *Categories*: Categorical elements that filter and focus teachers' perceiving and thinking. These comprise, e.g., pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) categories that teachers explicitly or implicitly chose as their filters, but also teachers' individual evaluation categories for assessing the success of their teaching.
 - *Orientations*: Generic or content-related beliefs and pedagogical attitudes about mathematics and its teaching and learning that implicitly or explicitly guide the teacher's perception and prioritization of jobs (see Schoenfeld, 2010, p. 29).

For explaining and promoting teachers' pathways of professional growth, we draw upon the well-established *Interconnected Model of Professional Growth* by Clarke and Hollingsworth (2002), which has been widely used, not only for describing and explaining, but also for designing PD programs promoting professional growth in modes of action and reflection. The model refers to four analytic domains (adapted by Prediger, 2024, see Figure 1): the *external domain* (with external sources of information, stimulus, or supportive curriculum materials for teachers), the *personal domain* (teachers' knowledge or attitudes), the *domain of practice* (which refers to a broad meaning of practice, but in which experimentation with new teaching practices in the above narrow sense can take place) and the *domain of consequence* (with salient outcomes such as students' motivation or learning gains to be observed). The

model identifies different mechanisms by which change in one domain can be associated with change in another. Rather than claiming simple mechanisms of transmission from the *external domain* via changing the *personal domain* to the *domain of practice* and then to the *domain of consequence*, Clarke & Hollingsworth emphasize an “interconnected, non-linear structure” between these domains and identify different “particular ‘change sequences’ and ‘growth networks’, giving recognition to the idiosyncratic and individual nature of teacher professional growth” (2002, p. 947). An example of such an individual change sequence is when teachers experiment in the domain of practice, monitoring students’ thinking in the domain of outcomes, and thereby expand their knowledge about student thinking in the individual domain, which is then the result of the change sequence rather than its start. The slightly adapted model that draws upon the introduced constructs of jobs, practices, categories, orientations, is printed in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Interconnected Model of Professional Growth (adapted by Prediger, 2024, from Clarke & Hollingsworth, 2002)

3. Empirical insights into the relevance and persistence of the success category of task completion in the Mastering Math project

In this section, the framework is illustrated and substantiated by empirical insights into our long-term Mastering Math project that aims at fostering the understanding of underprivileged students who are at risk of failing due to limited learning opportunities in earlier school years (Prediger et al., 2019; 2023). Within the Mastering Math project, curriculum materials with formative assessment tasks and enhancement tasks were developed and offered to teachers that help to discover these kinds of missing conceptual understanding and turn teachers’ attention to the needed understanding of basic concepts in which the multi-digit procedure is grounded (Hiebert & Wearne, 1996). In other contexts, our Mastering Math intervention program for fifth graders was shown to be effective for giving students safe access to the understanding of basic concepts, with significantly higher learning gains than in the control group (Prediger et al., 2019). However, the learning gains varied substantially and relied heavily on the effectiveness of the teachers, so further PD research was required for optimizing support

for all teachers and teacher teams. Within the PD research, we found that teachers' practices were driven by two main pairs of orientations (Prediger et al., 2023):

- *Conceptual orientation* rather than *procedural orientation*: Whereas goal setting and monitoring practices in procedural orientation mainly focus on procedural knowledge elements and prioritize them as learning goals, goal setting and monitoring practices in *conceptual orientation* focus on conceptual understanding of procedures and concepts (Zohar et al., 2001). With respect to differentiation practices, teachers tend to choose procedural tasks for low-achieving students and more conceptual tasks for higher achieving students (Beswick, 2007). When evaluating the success of teaching, teachers with a more conceptual orientation usually apply the *success category of conceptual learning progress*, whereas teachers with a more procedural orientation can apply the *success category of procedural learning progress*.
- *Long-term rather than short-term orientation*: Whereas goal setting and monitoring practices in short-term orientation only focus on the superficial performance in actual learning content, a long-term orientation helps teachers to focus on deep and sustainable mastery of learning content (Dweck, 1996; Watson & de Geest, 2005). In the following, we will show how the short-term orientation can completely change teachers' evaluation practices when only the *success category of task completion* is applied instead of monitoring students' (conceptual or procedural) learning progress.

3.1 *First vignette: Paul's differentiation practice with the success category of task completion minimizes learning opportunities*

The vignette was first published and analyzed in Prediger (2024). In the very first phase of our PD design research project Mastering Math, researcher facilitators from our Dortmund research team visited active schools in which teacher teams collaboratively developed their teaching practices to increase access to mathematics for at-risk students. In the first meeting with the facilitator researcher, one teacher team reported proudly that during the last nine months, they had differentiated their teaching material to adapt to their fifth graders' diverse mathematical abilities, through task-based individualized settings. After the meeting, the teacher team joined the research-practice-partnership.

In the first meeting, (the mathematics teacher here called) Paul reported about Suleika, one of their students with learning difficulties, and showed two of her products on multi-digit subtraction (in Figure 2):

Paul: Suleika can calculate the subtraction well, only the carries pose problems for her. But we can handle this successfully by differentiated tasks: I only give her subtractions without carries.

Described within the Model of Professional Growth (Figure 1), Paul, Maria, and their colleagues collaborated intensively, questioned and developed new practices of differentiation (*domain of practice* in Figure 1). However, Paul's utterance was a characteristic expression of this community's differentiating practices (repeatedly articulated in the conversation): students receive individualized tasks that are optimized on a level that they can master. Within this conceptualisation of success (*in the domain of consequence* in Figure 1), the collectively

established differentiation practice proved to be successful, as Suleika was able to complete her tasks.

However, in spite of these teachers' intense work, they could not develop more productive practices for enhancing Suleika's learning. Although Suleika's second product reveals serious struggle with place value understanding (see Figure 2), this was not treated by the teachers. Although the teachers agreed on the success of their instructional changes, Maria, Paul's colleague, had spent three months to convince the group to participate in the Mastering Math PD program with the university, as she wanted students to continue learning.

Figure 2

Snapshot from a community: Monitoring Suleika's learning

859 - 234 = 625

Rechenweg
erst die hundert dann die zehner dann die einer ist so nicht schwer

Translation: Strategy: first the hundreds, then the tens, then the ones, it's not that difficult

443 - 226 = 217

400 + 40 + 3 = 443
~~400~~ 300 - 200 = 100
~~40~~ 10 - 20 = 10
~~3~~ 3 - 2 = 1
 100 + 10 + 1 = 111

Maria's additional concerns that students "always forget" had also not yet entered the teachers' shared attention. For a deeper analysis of Suleika's assets and difficulties, the teacher team would have needed some PCK categories to unpack the error: Suleika mastered the basic skills of subtraction facts up to 10 and used them for multi-digit subtraction without carry. Subtraction with carry, however, is based on the conceptual understanding of decomposing numbers into digits. Suleika could not build on her mastery of multi-digit subtraction without carry due to limited fundamental place value understanding, visible in the highly indicative decomposition of 443 into 400-400-300 rather than 400+40+3.

As the teachers invested enormous efforts, it is important to understand why they were not reasoning about an accessible learning trajectory for Suleika from understanding basic concepts before acquiring procedures. This is not only a deficit of PCK categories, but also a consequence of their conceptualisations of success:

Within the Framework of Content-Related Teacher Expertise, the rationality of these teachers' differentiation practice can be traced back to a certain success category they applied to evaluate their teaching experiments: the teacher team's iterative pathway of action and reflection was driven by the shared idea that good inclusive classrooms are adaptive to students' abilities, and they realized it using the pedagogical tools of differentiated tasks and activity settings of individualized learning. The teacher group chose their differentiation practices by the *shared success category of task completion*. Applying this category based upon a short-term orientation, the teachers evaluated the short-term success by observing if the student was

able to complete the task with the given support and simplifications. Rather than focusing on how they can leverage their students' achievement to the zone of proximal development along the learning trajectory, these teachers optimize their differentiating practices in a way that all students can succeed to complete the task, even if the learning opportunities are taken away. Meanwhile, it was Maria's discontent with students not learning that led her to search new external input in initiating the research-practice-partnership within the Mastering Math PD project. In contrast to Paul, she adopted a long-term perspective in evaluating her success, yet needed three months to convince the others to search for more.

Figure 3

Substantiated Mastering Math Model of Professional Growth (Prediger, submitted)

The initial theorizing from this vignette later led to the substantiated Mastering Math Model of Professional Growth as depicted in Figure 3 (from Prediger, submitted). It is already printed here as an advance organizer and strengthened by further empirical insights in the next subsections.

From early experiences with teaching practices such as Paul's, we derived the need in the Mastering Math project to support teachers in monitoring students' conceptual understanding of basic concepts such as the place value understanding or the meaning of multiplication. So, we developed the Mastering math curriculum material (Prediger et al., 2019) with not only enhancement tasks following learning trajectories for all relevant basic arithmetic concepts (as identified by Gersten et al., 2009) in 45 modules, but also developed 45 conceptually focused formative assessment sheets, as suggested by Silver & Lane (1993).

In the Mastering Math PD program, teachers were invited to experiment with the curriculum materials, were offered some inputs for the PCK background of basic concepts, and in the Mastering Math school network meetings, the experiments were prepared, discussed and reflected (Figure 2). Once Maria could convince Paul and the rest of the team to shift their evaluation attention to students' learning, the team started to extend their differentiation practices.

3.2 *Second vignette: Lia’s compensation practice with the success category of task completion flattens deep conceptual learning opportunities*

The second vignette with the case of Lia (taken from Prediger, submitted) illustrates that the formative assessment sheets can indeed support teachers in extending a procedural orientation into a conceptual orientation and start with enhancement practices for conceptual understanding.

However, the success category of task completion can still be persistent and a hindrance for students’ deeper engagement. (The mathematics teacher here called) Lia was highly dedicated to supporting her at-risk students, so she participated in the Mastering Math PD program. She was satisfied about her teaching, but discontent with students’ remembrance: “We invest a lot in training multiplications such as 23×6 . But after three weeks, my low achievers make again $20 \times 6 + 3$. They simply forget too much and too quickly.”

After a year in the Mastering Math PD program and experimenting with the Mastering Math curriculum materials, multiplication was one of the last contents we worked on. Lia reported proudly:

“Only by these formative assessment tasks, I have realized that many of the kids don’t know the meaning of multiplication. I invested a lot in making all of them draw full dot arrays, not only 3 dots in vertical and 5 dots in an L-form, because we must see all 15 dots. With the dot array, one student surprised me by arguing *why* 13×5 must be $10 \times 5 + 3 \times 5$. Of, course, justification was too hard for the others.”

The representations that Lia mentioned are printed in Figure 4, together with an advance organizer on the analysis of her pathways of professional growth.

Figure 4

Lia’s changes in mathematical practices over three PD sessions and six months of experimenting with the Mastering Math curriculum materials

	Lia’s practices in 1 st PD session	Lia’s practices after six months in the PD program
Self-report of practices	Train procedures $23 \times 6 = 20 \times 6 + 3$ <i>wrong</i> $23 \times 6 = 20 \times 6 + 3 \times 6$ <i>correct</i>	Switch between representations: 3×5 can be represented by dot array $13 \times 5 = 10 \times 5 + 3 \times 5$ <i>because both have 85 dots</i>
Analysis		
Practices for three jobs	Set procedural learning goals Monitor correctness of procedures Foster simply by training	Set procedural and conceptual learning goals Monitor task completion Foster by supporting the task completion
Pedagogical tools	Procedural training tasks	Assessment tasks and enhancement tasks with multiple representations
Underlying categories of thinking and perceiving ex-/implicitly used	Categories for learning goals: • Procedure without errors Success category: • Task completion • Forgetting	Categories for learning goals (not yet further unpacked) • Dot arrays as the relevant representation • Procedure without errors and justified Success category: • Task completion • Still not conceptual learning progress
Underlying orientations	Procedural orientation Short-term orientation	Procedural and conceptual orientation Short-term orientation

According to the analysis presented in more detail in Prediger (submitted), Lia's pathway of professional growth can be described as follows (Figure 4): In the first PD session, Lia reported on training procedures and students forgetting them. From her report, we infer that she set procedural learning goals, and monitored only the correctness of students' procedures, so her main category of perceiving students' performance were procedures without error. Her main pedagogical tools were procedural training tasks, her fostering practices were restricted to training procedures without further learning opportunities. In total, her practices seemed to be consistently shaped by a procedural orientation. However, her short-term orientation was already slightly questioned by her discontent about students' forgetting, while the category of forgetting still assigns the responsibility of this not-lasting success to students, not to the teaching.

After three PD sessions and six months of experimenting with given curriculum material, Lia reported to have widened her practices, as she set also conceptual learning goals and monitored whether students could complete also conceptual tasks. In a certain way, this replicates findings about the role of formative assessments for installing conceptual learning goals (Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2018).

However, Lia continued to foster students by supporting them in completing tasks by correcting errors, even if these tasks now involve multiple representations. Her support for overcoming the misconception that 3×5 could be represented by an L-form (see Figure 4) was still restricted to the hint that 15 dots had to be visible, but not by articulating the underlying multiplicative structures by, e.g., three rows of fives (Götze & Baiker, 2021). She was not aware that by only alluding to the total number of dots, she could not yet enhance students' deep understanding because students continue simply switching representations. She widened her purely procedural orientation (often found in teachers of at-risk students Zohar et al., 2001; Beswick, 2007) by aspects of a conceptual orientation, but her surprise that a student justified the procedure with the dot array and her decision not to set the justification as a learning goal for all students indicates that she still fluctuated between procedural and conceptual orientation.

Lia illustrates a typical step on teachers' pathways of professional growth transcending from procedural to conceptual orientation, but yet stuck in a short-term orientation. Once having decided to set also conceptual learning goals, it can still happen that in the enactment of fostering practices, the conceptual learning opportunities are still limited by their in-the-moment focus on quick task completion rather than addresses mathematical structures in depth.

3.3 Prevalence of success category of task completion beyond the two cases

Teachers' individual *success category of task completion* instead of *learning progress* has been empirically identified in various case studies within the Mastering Math project and kindred projects (Prediger, 2024) and also by other researchers (Watson & Geest, 2005; Herbst, 2003). It is mostly connected to a short-term rather than long-term orientation (Prediger et al., 2016) and can co-occur with procedural or conceptual orientations (Prediger et al.,

2023). In various contexts and for different jobs, we could show that in short-term orientations, other practices turn out to be more rational than in long-term orientations (Watson & Geest, 2005; Prediger et al., 2016). For example, many fostering practices reveal immediate support is optimized to make students complete the task (we call them compensation practices, Prediger et al., 2023) and substitute deep learning opportunities (necessary in real enhancement practices) by shallow support not adaptive to the real learning needs.

Although the case of Paul might be an extreme case, there is still a considerable percentage of teachers who share his ideas. This can be shown by the following quantitative data from $n = 355$ mathematics teachers in the beginning of the first PD session. Teachers were shown the student case of Suleika's erroneous subtraction (see Figure 2) and asked to evaluate four teachers' approaches in dealing with Suleika's error on a 6-point likert scale. The results depicted in Figure 5 reveal that only 68% of the teachers completely rejected Paul's differentiation practice whereas 32% disagreed to some degrees (only 2% disagreed completely).

But also the evaluation rates for the second teaching practice can be interpreted as an evidence of prevalent short-term orientations and procedural orientations. Only 42% of the teachers fully disagreed to the tell-and-train practice for subtraction procedures (second practice in Figure 5), while only 35% of the teachers fully agreed to the need to work on Suleika's place value understanding (fourth practice in Figure 5). This most productive practice intended to be established in the Mastering Math project was fully rejected by 22% of the teachers in their first PD session.

Figure 5

Quantitative evidence for prevalence of short-term orientations and task completion (from SchuMaS project led by the author)

These results give also quantitative indications that the unproductive short-term oriented practices are still widespread among teachers and need to be intensively discussed in the PD program.

3.4 Partial shifts in success categories during the PD program

Although the *Mastering Math intervention program* proved effective on students' learning gains already in the first *field trial in 2015/16* (published in Prediger et al., 2019), the

large differences between the teachers’ degrees of effectiveness (Brophy, 2000) led us to continue to improve and investigate the Mastering PD program with more focused professional learning opportunities for teachers.

In order to unpack the PD learning content in more detail, we developed the already mentioned model of teacher expertise for fostering at-risk students’ understanding of basic concepts (Prediger et al., 2023), by systematizing the early case studies and earlier suggestions of what teachers need to learn (e.g., by Brodie, 2013; Beswick, 2007; Gheysens et al., 2020; Watson & Geest, 2005; and many others). The specified model of expertise contains several practices for the three jobs: *specifying learning content* (including unpacking mathematics learning content and setting learning goals for students, Morris et al., 2009), *monitoring students’ learning progress* with respect to these unpacked learning goals, and *enhancing student’s understanding* with respect to the unpacked learning goals (see Figure 6). For each job, we identified pairs of practices related to dual orientations (among them those found in the two vignettes in Section 3.1 and 3.2, procedural versus conceptual orientations, and short-term versus long-term orientations, but also others discussed in Prediger et al., 2023).

Figure 6

Results from the evaluation study of the Mastering Math PD program: effect sizes d from pre-PD to post-PD for each captured practice (light green color marks significant effects in intended direction, italics red marks in unintended direction)

For the *evaluation study on the PD level* conducted in 2019/20, we operationalized the practices in a standardized questionnaire of practices that teachers reported to adhere on a 5-point likert scale (from 0 to 5). We investigated the changes in (n = 95) teachers’ self-reported practices from the pre-questionnaire administered in the first PD session to the post-questionnaire after 9 months of PD program (consisting of weekly experimentations with the Mastering Math curriculum materials, prepared and reflected in six PD sessions of 3 h each). The

comparison of self-reported practices is summarized in Figure 6 by the effect sizes. Green colors marks significant changes in the intended direction and red color marks significant changes in the unintended direction (more details in Prediger et al., 2023).

For the practices in *procedural and conceptual orientations*, we identified significant changes for specifying practices and monitoring practices in intended directions (with effect sizes between $d = 0.27$ and 0.33), and a more focused unpacking of conceptual learning contents (as captured by vignette-based items, in the last row of Figure 6, with $d = 0.38$). For the enhancement practices, the changes in self-reports were not significant.

For the practices in *short-term or long-term orientation*, we found a significant and substantial reduction of goal-setting practices directed only to short-term repairs (with $d = 0.64$) with an intended push towards focusing basic concepts. However, for the enhancement practices, significantly more teachers ($d = 0.34$) than pre-PD reported compensation practices, even if this circumvents the enhancement of students' understanding (an example item of this scale is "When I realize that my low achievers lack basic concepts for solving a task, I scaffold them until they solve it nevertheless."). This means that after 9 months of participating in the PD program, teachers' short-term orientation had increased and the success category of task completion was even more dominantly articulated than before.

Although the Mastering Math PD program in 2019/20 showed many promising, intended effects with respect to a higher conceptual orientation and more long-term goal-setting practices, we had to realize that we still failed to shift teachers' individual success categories from task completion to learning progress (Prediger et al., 2023).

4. PD learning opportunity for shifting the success categories from task completion to learning progress

4.1 Task completion as success category in other DZLM projects

Within the research network of the German National Center for Mathematics Teacher Education (DZLM research network), task completion as a prevalent success category has also been identified in other contexts. I give only some examples with also external references to show the wide prevalence of this success category:

- In language-responsive mathematics teaching, some teachers only adopt approaches of simplifying language (Prediger, 2019). These compensation practices serve well to achieve task completion without language obstacles, yet they do not provide learning opportunities for amplifying students' language. Hence, "amplifying rather than simplifying" is the motto by which Walqui & Bunch (2019) try to shift teachers towards a stronger focus on students' language learning progress in a long-term orientation.
- Also in language-responsive mathematics teaching, many teachers tend to scaffold students' language production strongly (e.g., by sentence frames or prefabricated texts), yet without considering the fading out, so that students cannot sufficiently learn to express their ideas autonomously (Prediger, 2019). Although this kind of support can be efficient for guaranteeing task completion, van de Pol et al. (2010) emphasize that without planning and enacting the hand-over to independence, the term scaffolding should not even be used. In our PD program on language-responsive teaching, we have therefore

split scaffolding into two teacher jobs, supporting language and successively developing language (Prediger, 2019).

- In inclusive classrooms, many researchers have identified the distinction between what we call compensation practices (optimized for short-term task completion) and real enhancement practices (optimized for students' long-term learning progress), e.g., by distinguishing instructional adaptivity (differentiating the demands for allowing task completion) from curricular adaptivity (setting differentiated learning goals along students' learning trajectories, see Janney & Snell, 2006). In our MATILDA video study, we found that compensation practices (for language, mathematical prior knowledge, attention, etc.) occurred twice as often as enhancement practices (Prediger & Buró, 2021). So, we started to make this difference explicit in the PD programs and provided more professional learning opportunities for enhancement practices.
- Even in the PD program for enhancing mathematical potentials, when we worked with teachers who were willing to launch rich mathematics exploration tasks, we found that the success category of task completion still dominated the ways they monitored and intervened in students' problem-solving processes. Rather than strengthening typical germs of rich mathematical practices, they supported task completion in effective ways that yet reduced again the learning opportunities, this time for the general mathematical practices (Prediger, et al., 2016).

In each of these projects, teachers were highly engaged and wanted the best for their students' mathematical experiences. However, each time, the prevalent success category unnecessarily reduced the richness of students' mathematical learning opportunities. In each of these projects, we saw that for those teachers who shifted from task completion to learning progress as dominant success category, the pathways of professional growth profited substantially.

4.2 Consequences for enhanced PD opportunities

In the re-design of our PD programs, we have started to draw several consequences from the sketched findings about the prevalence of short-term orientations and the persistent success category of task completion. The following four consequences were most important:

- Explicit reflection opportunities on why task completion might be an insufficient success category because it might reduce rich learning opportunities to more shallow ones.
- Offers for formative assessment tools that support teachers in evaluating students' learning progress with respect to the PCK categories in view.
- Establishing long-term coherence of curricula as an important quality feature of quality mathematics instruction.
- Including more information about long-term learning progressions over several years to see the relevance of each content element in the long run.

Our current experiments with the enhanced PD opportunities in the SchuMaS PD program reveal first, humble indications that the combination of the four design consequences might enhance teachers' shifts from task completion to learning progress as major success category and might influence the ways they evaluate teaching practices. In the future, we need

to investigate more systematically in how far we can succeed in promoting the growth of teachers' long-term visions of successful mathematics teaching.

5. Discussion

The paper started with a broad view on policy perspectives, student perspectives and classroom observer perspectives on how to conceptualise success of mathematics instruction. Whereas the research community and policies seem to agree that students' learning gains should be the ultimate goal (with extended visions of mathematical literacy including multiple ambitious learning goals, see Silver & Lane, 1993), teaching practices observable in classrooms do not seem to be always in line with the instructional practices that have proven most effective for reaching these ambitious learning goals (Hiebert & Grouws, 2007; Brophy, 2000; Chi et al., 2018). In order to understand this realization gap, this plenary paper has focused teacher perspectives and investigated one particular aspect of teachers' conceptualisation of success. The case studies and some selected quantitative results revealed that teachers' *highly prevalent success category of task completion* can heavily influence their practices. This was already mentioned by others (Herbst, 2003; Watson & Geest, 2005), but still requires further investigations. In this plenary paper, I have collected findings how the success category of task completion becomes visible in different jobs for fostering at-risk students' mathematics learning, in setting goals, unpacking learning goals into detailed content elements, monitoring students' progress and fostering students' learning (Prediger, et al., 2023; Prediger & Buró, 2021).

Whereas constructive alignment of curriculum and assessment has widely been discussed, teachers' weak adherence to (ambitious, conceptually focused and also formative) assessments is not only connected to too narrow assessments (Silver & Lane, 1993; Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2018), but also to (often unconscious) routines that optimize the teaching for immediate task completion rather than for productive struggle (Henningsen & Stein, 1997; Chi et al., 2018). Although this heavily contributes to shallow learning opportunities rather than deep cognitive engagement (Chi et al., 2018), it is still rational in a certain teacher perspective that was explored here. It is rational when evaluating the teaching by immediate and struggle-free task completion.

As a consequence, PD programs should put more effort not only in improving the tasks and the assessments, but also in shifting teachers' success categories from task completion to learning progress, also in the in-the-moment decisions of daily teaching practices. The transparent report about a partial failure in our PD program (Prediger et al., 2023) strengthens the argument that much more effort is needed to understand the background of persistence (e.g., by investigating the teachers' performance and mastery orientation in the classical sense of Dweck, 1996) and to develop and investigate PD learning opportunities to support the overcoming of the unfaithful success category.

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